

READING COMPREHENSION PROBLEMS AND ACTIVITIES FOR IMPROVING READING ABILITIES OF LEARNERS

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Abstract: One of the main difficulties in learning a language is comprehending the given text. Many students have found that reading tasks are difficult as reading is fundamental section for other skills. In order to help student to comprehend the given text, teachers should facilitate a number of activities during the lesson. In this article, a number of activities are given in order to solve reading problems of learners.

Key words: comprehension, reading problems, scaffolding, differentiation, building learner autonomy.

Reading comprehension is one of the crucial aspects of language for academic success, especially for students learning English as a second language. Language learners face different types of comprehension problems in reading depending on their age and understanding level and teaching context. I have been teaching English as a L2 for 10 and 11 grades students and I become more aware of what kind of reading comprehension problems that encounter during learning English. A language consists of words that users of the language understand, use and apply their daily life. So that for comprehending a foreign language learning new words is one of the key points. Some of the learners have limited lexical range. So, restricted vocabulary hinders understanding of complex texts. English has a rich lexical resource which consists words, idioms, metaphors, and cultural references and phrases. They can be significant obstacles for learning to understand given texts. Knowing a word's basic meaning doesn't guarantee grasping its nuances in different contexts. According to Nonie K. Lesaux (2010) being aware of all the meaning of the words and different meaning of the words according to various contexts is essential. Another problem is

related comprehension degree of grammatical structures of the language. Complex sentence structures like long sentences with multiple clauses, embedded phrases, or unfamiliar grammatical structures can be difficult to parse.

Furthermore, discourse features of the language can cause misconception of the given text. Mainly, understanding how paragraphs connect, identifying main ideas vs. supporting details, and recognizing cohesive devices (transitions, pronouns) can be challenging to gist the text. Different text types (essays, narratives, technical writing) have unique structures and language that students may not be familiar with.

Cognitive and processing factors also affect reading the text. Holding multiple pieces of information in mind while decoding and making connections can be overwhelming. This may happen not only to understand given texts in a foreign language but also in their native languages.

Lack of familiarity with the topic, cultural context, or historical references can make comprehension difficult. For instance, English and Uzbek languages are distinct languages and the people who are using these languages to communicate do not come from familiar cultural background. Prior experiences with different reading materials, purposes, and approaches can influence how students approach English texts. So, Uzbek students have difficulty to understand cultural context, or historical references in English.

Reading comprehension can be related to individual as personality traits can play a role in this case. Fear of making mistakes or feeling inadequate can hinder comprehension. Lack of interest in the topic or a perceived lack of relevance can lead to disengagement and poor comprehension.

In order to improve reading comprehension of the students, a number of methods should be carried out by teachers also students themselves.

Firstly, explicit vocabulary instruction should be integrated like focusing on high-frequency words, academic vocabulary, and strategies for independent word learning. According to D. Yapp (2021) the instructors should help students identify and use surrounding words and sentences to infer word meanings.

Word roots, prefixes, and suffixes are key elements of the language which can affect general meaning of the text. Teaching common word parts to unlock the meaning of unfamiliar words is effective to differentiate word formation in the context.

Sentence unpacking and grammar practice are essential such as breaking down complex sentences, teaching signal words, and providing practice with different grammatical structures.

Teacher should explain how to preview text, identify main ideas, make inferences, and monitor their comprehension. Before giving a text, brainstorming should be applied as it helps learners to discuss the topic, relate it to students' experiences, and elicit what they already know. After this stage, quickly glance through the text to get the gist or find specific information should be asked from learners. This encourages students to make guesses about the text based on the title, headings, or illustrations. During reading the given text, highlighting key ideas, writing notes in the margins, or asking questions as they read should be done by learners. After doing reading task, the teacher should facilitate class or small group discussions to share interpretations, ask questions, and clarify misunderstandings. Also, the teacher should provide opportunities for students to reflect on their reading, express their opinions, and make connections to their own lives. Another useful task is writing summary of what they have learned from the text.

Scaffolding and differentiation should be applied during the lesson as students are very different in personality traits, cultural background and understanding level. Offering support through graphic organizers, timelines, organize information and visualize relationships between ideas, simplified texts, peer collaboration, and individualized instruction are useful methods that teachers can use.

Building learner autonomy is neglected by many English language teachers. Fostering a positive learning environment like creating a safe and supportive classroom where students feel comfortable taking risks and asking for help can be effective to help students to comprehend given texts.

In sum up, understanding these challenges and implementing effective teaching strategies, educators can support 11th-grade ESL students in developing their English reading comprehension skills.

Reference:

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